

Death by a Thousand Papercuts: An Overview of the Threatening Partnership Between Transnational Criminal Organizations and Intelligence Services in Russia and China

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Russia and China seek nothing less than a comprehensive reordering of international relations.¹ To effectively defeat Western order, they have engaged in premediated, long-term strategies that – to paraphrase Mark Galeotti – weaponize every available resource available to achieve their aim.² Specifically, Russia and China increasingly employ criminal organizations and networks for hacking and cyberespionage operations.³ To confront the evolution of warfare in an era of global risk,⁴ practitioners and civilians must understand three things: (i) the actors behind international attacks, (ii) the nature of these attacks, and (iii) the motivations driving these attacks.

¹ Calder Walton, “The New Spy Wars: How China and Russia Use Intelligence Agencies to Undermine America.” *Foreign Affairs*, 19 July 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/china/russia-china-intelligence-new-spy-wars-undermine-america>.

² Mark Galeotti and Nicholas Eftimiades, Gareme P. Herd, “Russia and China’s Intelligence and Information Operations Nexus: Implications for Global Strategic Competition?” *Strategic Competition Seminar Series #4*, 14 December 2021, <https://www.marshallcenter.org/en/publications/clock-tower-security-series/strategic-competition-seminar-series/russia-and-chinas-intelligence-and-information-operations-nexus>.

³ David Klepper, “Cyber criminals are increasingly helping Russia and China target the U.S. and allies, Microsoft says,” *AP News*, 15 October 2024, <https://apnews.com/article/microsoft-russia-china-iran-israel-cyberespionage-cyber-d3a22dd2dcea32615ac15ed4fb951541>.

⁴ Antonio Graceffo, “Rethinking Defense Strategy for a New Era of Total War,” *Geopolitical Monitor*, 18 November 2024, <https://www.geopoliticalmonitor.com/rethinking-defense-strategy-for-a-new-era-of-total-war/>.

The partnerships Russia and China have established with transnational criminal organizations (TCOs) enable these states to proliferate the number of cyber operations,⁵ mortally wounding their adversaries through a thousand papercuts. These cybercriminals sow disruption and uncertainty, threaten critical infrastructure,⁶ and create a fog not domineered by the rule of law or oversight. Moreover, attribution – already a challenge in cyberattacks⁷ – is further complicated as one must learn to discern the actor behind the actor.

Effects of State and Criminal Collusion in the Cyber Realm

State collusion with criminal networks increases the number of attacks⁸ as well as potentially impacting psychological wellbeing through constant vigilance and uncertainty. Modern society inhabits a fragile world, depending ever more on cyber capabilities, technologies, and complex networks. Disruptions to these networks can seriously affect critical infrastructures and capacities.⁹

Cyber-attacks singularly introduce a systemic complexity to warfare in three ways: (1) expanding the spectrum of conflict,¹⁰ (2) drawing non-state actors into the environment of warfare,¹¹ and (3) presenting a total war framework which interweaves economic, military, and citizen spheres.¹² These factors are present within cyberattacks and must be effectively understood and countered. Failure to do so will put the U.S. and its allies at risk of being slowly drained, cut by cut. Inability to understand the motivations behind these attacks will destabilize and dishearten members of a democratic society, thus undermining the national will to fight and resist.¹³

⁵ Homeland Security, “Homeland Threat Assessment 2025,” *Office of Intelligence and Analysis*, 2 October 2024, https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/2024-10/24_0930_ia_24-320-ia-publication-2025-hta-final-30sep24-508.pdf, Pg 23.

⁶ Homeland Security, “Homeland Threat,” Pg 23.

⁷ Jake Sepich, “The Evolution of Cyber Attribution,” *American University: Center for Security, Innovation, and New Technology*, 19 April 2023, <https://www.american.edu/sis/centers/security-technology/the-evolution-of-cyber-attribution.cfm>.

⁸ Klepper, “Cyber criminals.”

⁹ CISA, “Critical Infrastructure Sectors,” *America’s Cyber Defense Agency*, CISA, accessed 2 November 2024, <https://www.cisa.gov/topics/critical-infrastructure-security-and-resilience>.

¹⁰ Graceffo, “Rethinking Defense Strategy.”

¹¹ Klepper, “Cyber criminals.”

¹² Graceffo, “Rethinking Defense Strategy.”

¹³ McNearney et al, “What is Will to Fight and Why Does It Matter?” in *National Will to Fight: Why Some States Keep Fighting and Others Don’t*, edited by McNearney, et al, (Rand Corporation, 28 September 2018), https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RR2477.html, pg 30.

Aims and Motivations

America's adversaries are weaponizing things previously not weaponized. This weaponization creates a new realm of warfare¹⁴ wherein nothing is untouchable. To adequately understand the risks, one must recognize the expanding repertoire of actors and the factors that motivate them. Calder Walton with *Foreign Affairs* paints a bleak picture: while the U.S. was pre-occupied by terrorism, Russia and China's intelligence agencies were at work "to damage U.S. national security, undermine Western democracies, and steal as many scientific and technical secrets as possible."¹⁵ These intelligence agencies have not only targeted state secrets, but also private sector companies, research, critical infrastructure, and individual data.¹⁶ Their methods have diversified beyond theft to encompass legal access to data through user agreements.¹⁷

Specifically, Russia seeks to reclaim what it perceives as its rightful place in the global affairs,¹⁸ and China combines economic, technologic, diplomatic, and kinetic power to pose a multifaceted threat.¹⁹ China does so in pursuit of the restoration of the Middle Kingdom and global primacy.²⁰ In essence, Russia and China seek nothing less than to overturn the international order post-Cold War.²¹

Partnership

Galeotti, et al. argue that Russia employs an "intense tempo of operations."²² Highly willing to accept operational failures, Russia throws Plans A-G at its adversaries in rapid succession,²³ willing to use nearly any means to achieve the comprehensive nature of its goal. As partners, TCOs appeal to Russia and China because their fluidity,

¹⁴ Graceffo, "Rethinking Cyber Defense."

¹⁵ Walton, "The New Spy Wars."

¹⁶ Michael J. Orlando, "Protect Your Organization from the Foreign Intelligence Threat." *National Counterintelligence and Security Center*, N.D, <https://www.dni.gov/files/NCSC/documents/SafeguardingOurFuture/12.13.2021%20Protect%20Your%20Org%20from%20the%20Foreign%20Intel%20Threat.pdf>.

¹⁷ Center for Internet Security, "The Chinese Communist Party (CCP): A Quest for Data Control," *Center for Internet Security*, 14 August 2024, <https://www.cisecurity.org/insights/blog/the-chinese-communist-party-ccp-a-quest-for-data-control>.

¹⁸ Terri Moon Cronk, "Top Intelligence Chiefs Testify on Global Threats." U.S. Department of Defense, 10 May 2022, <https://www.defense.gov/News/News-Stories/Article/Article/3027208/top-intelligence-chiefs-testify-on-global-threats/>.

¹⁹ Cronk, "Top Intelligence Chiefs."

²⁰ Galeotti, et al., "Russia and China's Intelligence."

²¹ Walton, "New Spy Wars."

²² Galeotti, et al., "Russia and China's Intelligence."

²³ Ibid.

criminality, and sophistication can destabilize adversaries, access resources, and evade international sanctions.²⁴ These benefits emerge particularly in the cyber realm, where attribution is already murky game²⁵ and adding actors to the stage serves to compound confusion.

Furthermore, criminal hackers have no need to dance the mitigating diplomatic dance, as their standing on the international stage and legitimacy as a group have already been compromised by criminality. Russia evaded international liability for the actions of the Wagner Group because the Wagner Group was considered ontologically distinct from the Russian state.²⁶ The international capacity must be strengthened to tie cyber operations to actors and their sponsors, attributing operations to criminal and state collusion; by attributing operations to states, the states may be held accountable.²⁷

TCOs, meanwhile, partner with states such as Russia and China for financial and legal benefits.²⁸ Working for these states can be highly lucrative and affords some degree of government protection.²⁹ This protection invites further chaos to the global arena through creating a quasi-legitimate space for criminal networks and drawing these networks at least partially beneath state control. TCOs share the goal of weakening democratic institutions, thus undermining the institutional ability to prosecute, contain, and eliminate criminal groups.³⁰ The disruption of democracies is mutually advantageous to Russia, China, and TCOs.

Criminal Operations in Action

Mike Orlando, Acting Director for the National Counterintelligence and Security Center, warns that conflict is no longer contained to a battlefield, but brought into America's very homes through our "power grids, our computer networks, our laboratories and research facilities, our financial institutions, our healthcare providers,

²⁴ The White House, "2023 White House Strategy to Combat Transnational Organized Crime." *The White House*, December 2023, https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Transnational-Organized-Crime_FINAL_Dec2023.pdf, pg 4.

²⁵ Jake Sepich, "The Evolution of Cyber Attribution."

²⁶ Gregory P. Noone, et al, "Status of the Wagner Group and can Russia be held accountable for their crimes?" *PILPG: A Global Pro Bono Law Firm*, 8 October 2024, <https://www.publicinternationallawandpolicygroup.org/lawyer-ing-justice-blog/2024/10/8/status-of-the-wagner-group-and-can-russia-be-held-accountable-for-their-crimes>.

²⁷ Noone, et al, "Status of the Wagner Group."

²⁸ The White House, "2023 White House Strategy," pg. 3.

²⁹ Klepper, "Cyber criminals."

³⁰ The White House, "2023 White House Strategy, pg 4.

and our federal, state, local, and tribal governments.”³¹ Through hacking and cyberoperations, Russia and China can reach beyond a battlefield³² to destabilize the inner workings of their adversaries’ societies (such as through critical infrastructure).³³

Investigators found that a Russian criminal network hacked over 50 Ukrainian military devices in June 2024.³⁴ According to Microsoft, there was no financial motive beyond state payment,³⁵ highlighting Russia’s willingness to contract TCOs. Additionally, this outsourcing may indicate that Russia does not care so much about the *efficacy* of the attack as the *presence* of the attack. Knowing that Russia has hacked 50 Ukrainian military devices may well have a destabilizing effect on Ukraine, sowing doubt, internal confusion, and disruption. Russia employs this strategy (sowing doubt, confusion, and disruption) in democratic elections across the globe, aiming to destabilize adversaries for its own political benefit.³⁶ These cyberoperations present a mind game, causing Ukraine (among other nations) to question the security of their networks and wonder what is real, secure, and true.

While unaffiliated with Russia or China, a cybercriminal group with ties to Iran attempted to sell personal information they stole from an Israeli dating site.³⁷ The goal of the criminal infiltration was profit and Israeli embarrassment,³⁸ highlighting the changing nature of modern warfare and the threat of a thousand papercuts. This conflict cannot be won by a more significant military force or even cyber might, but it requires resolve and attention to the objective of America’s adversaries so that American practitioners may exactly where to throw their weight.

Conclusion

The face and scope of conflict has changed, and the U.S. must face these comprehensive changes with clarity, understanding, and courage. As Microsoft VP of Customer Security and Trust Tom Burt claims, this growing trend of interlocking state

³¹ Orlando, “Protect Your Organization.”

³² Graceffo, “Rethinking Cyber Defense.”

³³ CISA, “Critical Infrastructure Sectors.”

³⁴ Klepper, “Cyber criminals.”

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Nicholas Riccardi, “US warns of a Russian effort to sow doubt over the election outcomes in democracies around the globe,” *AP News*, 20 October 2023, <https://apnews.com/article/election-interference-misinformation-voter-fraud-russia-cabdacd3d4a1dd8296a1419b03ed751d>.

³⁷ Klepper, “Cyber criminals.”

³⁸ *Ibid.*

and cybercriminal activities “shows how far America’s adversaries will go to weaponize the internet.”³⁹ One must ask whether America recognizes that threats can come from any angle in this modern conflict. Adversaries such as Russia and China are weaponizing every domain and resource. They are not constrained by the American or international consensus of what constitutes warfare because they are not interested in a relative seat at the table but rather in destroying that table and creating a new one.⁴⁰ The international system Russia and China seek to establish (by every means possible)⁴¹ would not align with democratic values such as the equality of states and individuals, human flourishing, freedom, and truth.

Citizens and practitioners must recognize the mounting threat of cyber-attacks from diverse actors.⁴² The developing partnership between adversarial states and TCOs severely impacts national security by creating another battleground much closer to home, extending the reach of Russian and Chinese arms, and sowing further discord in modern conflict. Warfare and conflict are evolving beyond major military conflicts⁴³ to mirror the deafening roar of a thousand small drums. As a society, Americans must be aware of this threat in order to withstand its mental and emotional toll.

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Walton, “New Spy Wars.”

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Homeland Security, “Homeland Threat,” pg 22-23.

⁴³ Graceffo, “Rethinking Cyber Defense.”